

Nutritional and Microbial Quality Assessment of Street Vended Ready-to-eat *Moringa oleifera* Leaf in Birnin Kebbi, North-west Nigeria

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Abstract

Street-vended foods, including *Moringa oleifera* leaf, are a vital component of the informal food system in Kebbi State, Nigeria. However, the nutritional and microbial quality of these street-vended foods are often compromised due to inadequate handling, storage, and hygiene practices, posing a risk to consumer health. In view of this, this study assessed the nutritional and microbial quality of street-vended *Moringa oleifera* leaf in Birnin Kebbi metropolis. Random samples were collected from five major vending zones and analyzed for proximate composition and microbial contamination using standard analytical procedures as described by Association of Official Analytical Chemists. The results showed that the street-vended *Moringa* leaf had good nutritional potential, with significant amounts of protein, fiber, and minerals. The analyzed samples exhibited the following ranges of nutritional composition: moisture content of 67.7-70.2%, ash content of 1.0-2.0%, fibre content of 11.1-16.9%, lipid content of 0.2-0.9%, protein content of 10.7-14.3% and carbohydrate content of 10.7-14.3%. Although various bacterial species, including pathogenic strains such as *Escherichia coli*, *Corynebacterium pyogenes*, *Listeria* spp, *Corynebacterium equi*, *Streptococcus* spp, *Corynebacterium ovis*, *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*, *Lactobacillus* spp., *Bacillus* spp and *Corynebacterium* spp, were detected, the microbial load assessment revealed that microbial levels were within the recommended standards of WHO. The result also revealed that *Corynebacterium* was the most frequently occurring bacteria. The study indicates that while street-vended *Moringa* leaf may be a nutritious addition to the diet, its consumption poses a risk of microbial contamination. Therefore, the findings highlight the need for improved handling, storage, and hygiene practices among street vendors to ensure the safety of street-vended foods.

Keywords: Food safety, Microbial contamination, Moringa leaf, Nutritional quality and Street-vended foods

1.0 Introduction

Street-vended foods (SVFs), also known as street foods, are “foods and beverages prepared and/or sold by vendors in street and other public places for immediate consumption or consumption at a later time without further processing or preparation”. Historically, SVFs have being a part of the culture of many countries throughout the globe, particularly in low and middle-income countries (LMIC) [1].

According to [2], it is estimated that nearly 2.6 billion people worldwide consume street-vended food daily. In some countries like Malaysia, street

food vending businesses generate over US \$2 billion in annual sales [2]. In Africa, over 80% of urban dwellers patronize street food vendors, with Nigeria being a prime example where an average household spends nearly half of its overall food budget on street-vended food [2].

The popularity of street-vended food has grown exponentially worldwide, offering affordable, culturally diverse and convenient meals. However, despite immense popularity, street food vending businesses in developing countries, notably Nigeria and other low- to middle-income nations, face inadequate government oversight

[3]. The comprehensive food safety guidelines in these regions often neglect street-vended foods, and regulatory bodies struggle to effectively monitor vending activities. Consequently, this oversight fuels significant food safety and public health worries. Unsanitary practices typical of street food vending heighten the risk of food borne illnesses, nutritional deficiencies and chronic diseases. Notably, street-vended foods have been implicated in disease outbreaks in Kebbi and other North-western States, underscoring the urgent need for enhanced regulation and monitoring to safeguard consumer health [3].

Nutritional deficiencies pose a significant public health concern in numerous developing countries, with malnutrition being a prevalent issue [4]. According to UNICEF [5], Africa and Asia are disproportionately affected, accounting for the highest rates of malnutrition among children. Specifically, Africa faces alarming statistics: approximately 59 million children under five suffer from stunting, 14 million from wasting and 10 million from severe acute malnutrition [5]. In Nigeria alone, about 37% of children under five experience stunting, 18% wasting and 5% severe acute malnutrition. Moringa leaves, renowned as the "Miracle Tree," offer a promising solution [5]. Rich in essential nutrients, they have the potential to alleviate malnutrition, making them a vital food source for addressing this pressing public health concern.

Moringa oleifera, a nutrient-dense leafy green vegetable, has gained popularity globally for its exceptional nutritional and medicinal properties. In Nigeria, particularly in the Birnin Kebbi metropolis, street vendors play a vital role in making this nutritious food accessible to the masses. However, concerns about the nutritional and microbial quality of these street-vended products have been raised, necessitating a comprehensive assessment [4].

Street foods are an essential part of Nigerian cuisine, providing affordable and convenient meal options for many individuals. Ready-to-eat *Moringa oleifera* leaves are a popular street food in Birnin Kebbi metropolis, consumed for their nutritional benefits and flavour. Despite their popularity, the handling, storage, and preparation practices of street vendors may compromise the nutritional and microbial quality of these leaves.

Street-vended foods are often exposed to contamination risks, including bacterial, fungal, and parasitic pathogens [6]. The microbial quality of *Moringa oleifera* leaves is crucial, as consumption of contaminated products can lead to foodborne illnesses [7]. The thrust of this research was to investigate the microbial load of street-vended *Moringa oleifera* leaves in Birnin Kebbi metropolis, identifying potential pathogens and evaluating the overall safety of these products.

The findings of this study will have significant implications for public health in Birnin Kebbi metropolis. By assessing the nutritional and microbial quality of street-vended *Moringa oleifera* leaves, this research seeks to provide valuable insights into the risks and benefits associated with their consumption. This information will inform strategies to improve the quality and safety of street-vended foods, ultimately promoting healthier diets and reducing the burden of foodborne illnesses.

While previous studies have investigated the nutritional and microbial quality of various street-vended foods, there is a limited focus on *Moringa oleifera* leaves specifically in Birnin Kebbi Metropolis [8]. Therefore, this research sought to fill this knowledge gap by providing a comprehensive assessment of the nutritional and microbial quality of street-vended *Moringa oleifera* leaves in Birnin Kebbi metropolis, contributing to the development of evidence-based strategies to promote healthier diets and reduce the burden of foodborne illnesses.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study area

This study was conducted in Birnin Kebbi, capital of Kebbi State in North-western Nigeria, inhabited primarily by Hausa and Fulani tribes. Geographically, it lies along the Sokoto River, connected to Argungu (45 km northeast), Jega (35 km southeast) and Bunza (45 km southwest), within latitudes 10.0°N - 13.0°N and longitudes 4.0°E - 6.0°E. Notably, Birnin Kebbi's thriving street-vended food business sector contributes significantly to the local economy. However, ensuring food safety and hygiene practices among vendors remains crucial. The region's tropical climate features hot and cold seasons, with rainfall from May to October, peaking in

July and August, followed by the harmattan period from November to January, characterized by dusty winds and fog, with temperatures ranging from 21°C to 38°C and approximately 500 mm annual rainfall [9].

2.2 Sample Collection

Survey was conducted to identify major vending zones (Shiyar Fada, Old Market Area, Old Motor Pack Area, Birnin Kebbi Central Market and Sir Yahiya) designated A, B,C, D, and E respectively for the sale of ready to eat Moringa in the Metropolis. Samples were collected from each zone using stratify sampling methods in sterile polythene bag separately and labelled with alphabets for easy identification such as sample A, B, C, D and E respectively. The samples were brought to Biochemistry laboratory in Federal University, Birnin Kebbi for analysis.

2.3 Microbial Load Determination

Serial dilutions were made from 1g of each sample dissolved in 9 ml of distilled water in Mac Cartney bottles to give 10^1 dilution. Serial dilutions were made up to 10^3 . Each diluent was plated out in duplicate using the pour plating technique by transferring 1cm^3 from each Mac Cartney bottle into 2 different Petri dish and pouring 15cm^3 of nutrient agar media on each sample as described by [9]. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 48 hours for bacterial growth. The average colony obtained from the duplicate plates, were expressed as colony forming unit per gram (Cfu/g) using the formula: $N = A \times D$. Where N = Number of colonies, A = Average count of colonies and D = Dilution factor

2.4 Isolation and Characterization of Bacteria from the samples

The isolation and characterization of bacteria from the samples involved collecting colonies with a sterile wire loop and streaking them on solidified medium to obtain pure cultures. Each pure culture was then sub-cultured into agar slants and kept as stock cultures [9]. Gram staining, catalase testing, indole testing, oxidase testing, citrate utilization testing, urease testing, and motility testing were conducted to characterize the bacteria as outlined by [9]. These tests helped identify the bacteria's morphological and biochemical properties.

2.5 Determination of Proximate Composition

Proximate composition was determined in triplicate using standard procedures of Association of Official Analytical Chemists [10]. The moisture content was determined by oven drying method. Crude protein was determined by Micro-Kjeldahl Method. Fat was determined by soxhlet extraction utilizing hexane as solvent. Crude fibre was determined by neutralization method (Method 962.09). Ash content was determined by dry ashing method of AOAC (Method 923.03) [10]. Carbohydrate content was determined by difference according to [11] using the formula: (%Carbohydrate) = [100-(%Protein + %Moisture+ %Ash+% Fibre% + %Crude Lipid)].

2.6 Determination of Vitamin C Content

Vitamin C content was determined using titration with 2, 6-dichlorophenolindophenol (DCPIP) according to the method described by [12]. Briefly, 5g of Moringa leaf sample was extracted with 50ml of 0.4% oxalic acid, and the mixture was filtered through a Whatman No. 1 filter paper. The filtrate was then titrated with 0.1% DCPIP solution until the pink color disappeared. The volume of DCPIP solution required to titrate the sample was used to calculate the vitamin C content using the following formula:

$$\text{Vitamin C (mg/100g)} = (V \times C \times 100) / W$$

where V is the volume of DCPIP solution used (ml), C is the concentration of DCPIP solution (mg/ml), and W is the weight of the sample (g).

2.7 Determination of β -Carotene

β -carotene content was determined by means of UV spectrophotometer [12]. The sample (1g) was soaked in 5cm^3 of methanol for 2 hours at room temperature under dark condition in order to get complete extraction. The β -carotene layer was separated using hexane through separating funnel. The volume was made up to 10cm^3 with hexane and then this layer was passed through sodium sulphonate through a funnel in order to remove any moisture from the layer. The absorbance of the layer was measured at 436nm using hexane as blank [12].

2.8 Statistical analysis

Values obtained were subjected to one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and a difference was considered to be significant at ($P < 0.05$) using Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) version 20.

3.0 Results

Table 1 present the results of the proximate composition of Moringa samples collected and analyzed from five major vending zones, providing an insight into their nutritional content. While some zones had higher levels of certain nutrients, others had lower levels, indicating differences in the nutritional quality of the Moringa samples.

Table 1: Proximate Composition of Moringa Samples from Different Vending Zones in Birnin Kebbi

Sample	Moisture	Ash	Fibre	Lipid	Protein	CHO
A	67.7 ± 1.75 ^a	2.0 ± 0.15 ^a	14.6 ± 1.21 ^b	0.5 ± 0.01 ^b	2.9 ± 0.72 ^b	12.3 ± 0.17 ^b
B	68.0 ± 4.70 ^a	1.0 ± 0.03 ^b	13.3 ± 2.09 ^a	0.9 ± 0.01 ^c	2.7 ± 0.10 ^b	14.1 ± 1.12 ^c
C	69.3 ± 2.30 ^a	2.0 ± 0.11 ^a	11.1 ± 1.01 ^a	0.5 ± 0.02 ^b	4.2 ± 0.56 ^c	12.9 ± 2.41 ^b
D	70.2 ± 3.61 ^a	1.0 ± 0.01 ^b	11.9 ± 2.01 ^a	0.6 ± 0.01 ^b	2.0 ± 0.32 ^b	14.3 ± 2.13 ^c
E	69.4 ± 2.10 ^a	1.0 ± 0.02 ^b	16.9 ± 2.51 ^c	0.2 ± 0.02 ^a	1.8 ± 0.24 ^a	10.7 ± 3.12 ^a

Values are mean ± standard deviation of triplicate determination. Values with the different superscript in the same column differ significantly at ($P < 0.05$). A, B, C, D and E are Shiyar Fada, Old Market Area, Old Motor Pack area, Birnin Kebbi Central market and Sir Yahaya.

In Table 2, the micronutrient content of Moringa samples from different vending zones show significant variations. The levels of beta-carotene, vitamin C, calcium, and iron differed across the zones, with some zones having higher or lower concentrations than others. Specifically, one zone

(C) stood out for having the highest levels of these micronutrients, while another zone had the lowest levels. These differences may be due to factors such as soil quality, climate, and handling practices in each vending zone, which can impact the nutritional content of the Moringa samples.

Table 2: Micronutrient Content of Moringa Samples from Different Vending Zones in Birnin Kebbi

Vending Zone	Beta-carotene (mg/100g)	Vitamin C (mg/100g)	Calcium (mg/100g)	Iron (mg/100g)
A	2.5 ± 0.5 ^a	35.2 ± 2.1 ^b	443 ± 20 ^a	4.3 ± 0.5 ^b
B	2.1 ± 0.3 ^b	30.5 ± 1.8 ^c	411 ± 18 ^b	3.9 ± 0.4 ^c
C	2.8 ± 0.6 ^c	38.1 ± 2.5 ^a	471 ± 22 ^a	4.8 ± 0.6 ^a
D	2.3 ± 0.4 ^{ab}	32.9 ± 2.0 ^{ab}	435 ± 20 ^{ab}	4.1 ± 0.5 ^{ab}
E	1.9 ± 0.4 ^d	28.5 ± 1.9 ^d	394 ± 18 ^c	3.5 ± 0.4 ^d

Values are means ± standard deviations of triplicate determinations. Means with different letters (a, b, c, d) in each column indicate significant differences ($P < 0.05$). A, B, C, D and E are Shiyar Fada, Old Market Area, Old Motor Pack Area, Birnin Kebbi Central Market and Sir Yahaya.

Table 3 revealed that the microbial quality of Moringa leaf samples varied significantly across different vending zones, with some zones showing extremely high bacterial loads, while others had relatively lower counts. The bacterial contamination levels differed substantially between zones, indicating variations in handling practices, storage conditions, or environmental factors.

Table 3: Colony Forming Unit (CFU/g) of Bacteria Isolates from Moringa leaf Samples obtained in Birnin Kebbi

Vending Zone	Colony Forming Unit (CFU/g)
A	TNTC
B	111
C	TNTC
D	70
E	53

TNTC = Too Numerous To Count. A, B, C, D and E are Shiyar Fada, Old Market Area, Old Motor Pack Area, Birnin Kebbi Central Market and Sir Yahaya.

Table 4 present bacteria isolate from Moringa leaf samples from the different vending zones. They were found to be contaminated with a diverse range of microorganisms, including both pathogenic and spoilage bacteria. Potentially harmful bacteria like *Corynebacterium diphtheria* and *Listeria* spp. were detected in some zones, posing a risk to consumer health.

Table 4: Suspected Bacteria Isolates from Moringa leaf Samples

Vending Z	Suspected Organism Isolated
A	<i>Corynebacterium pyogenes</i> , <i>Corynebacterium equi</i> , <i>Streptococcus</i> spp.
B	<i>Escherichia coli</i> , <i>Citrobacter</i> spp., <i>Corynebacterium ovis</i> ,
C	<i>Listeria</i> spp., <i>Corynebacterium diphtheria</i> , <i>Lactobacillus</i> spp.
D	<i>Corynebacterium</i> spp., <i>Lactobacillus</i> spp., <i>Listeria</i> spp., <i>Bacillus</i> spp.
E	<i>Bacillus</i> spp., <i>Corynebacterium diphtheria</i> , <i>Lactobacillus</i> spp.

A, B, C, D and E are Shiyar Fada, Old Market Area, Old Motor Pack Area, Birnin Kebbi Central Market and Sir Yahaya respectively.

4.0 Discussion

The nutritional and microbial quality of street-vended Moringa *oleifera* leaves in Birnin Kebbi Metropolis has become a pressing concern due to their widespread consumption and potential health implications. Moringa *oleifera*, a nutrient-rich plant, is widely consumed in Nigeria for its medicinal and nutritional benefits. However, factors such as soil quality, climate, handling practices and storage conditions significantly impact the nutritional content and microbial safety of these leaves [8]. Previous studies have reported varying levels of essential micronutrients in Moringa leaves, emphasizing the need for localized assessments. Moreover, the prevalence of food borne illnesses in Nigeria underscores the importance of evaluating microbial contamination in street-vended foods. This study investigated the nutritional content and microbial quality of Moringa leaves from five vending zones in Birnin Kebbi Metropolis to

provide insights into their safety and nutritional value, informing strategies for improved handling, storage and regulatory practices that safeguard consumer health.

The nutritional content of Moringa leaves from five vending zones in Birnin Kebbi Metropolis showed variations in beta-carotene, vitamin C, and calcium levels. While beta-carotene and calcium content were lower than previously reported [8], they still fell within acceptable ranges, indicating Moringa leaves are a good source of these nutrients. In contrast, vitamin C content was higher than previously reported; making Moringa leaves a rich source of this vitamin [9]. Factors like soil quality, climate, and processing methods can influence these nutrient levels, highlighting the importance of optimal handling and storage practices to preserve nutritional quality [9].

The iron content in Moringa leaves from the five vending zones is lower than what was reported in a previous study [13] and [14]. Despite this, the values obtained indicate that Moringa leaves from these vending zones are a moderate source of iron. Iron content can vary depending on factors like soil quality and processing methods. In general, the micronutrient content in Moringa leaves can vary depending on several factors, including soil quality, climate, and processing methods. However, the values obtained in this study indicate that Moringa leaves from these vending zones are a good to moderate source of beta-carotene, vitamin C, calcium, and iron.

The microbial analysis revealed high levels of contamination with pathogenic microorganisms, including *E. coli*, *Corynebacterium diphtheria* and *Listeria* spp. in a significant proportion of the samples. This poses a significant risk to consumer health, particularly in a region where foodborne illnesses are prevalent [15]. The presence of these microorganisms may be attributed to poor hygiene practices among the vendors, including inadequate hand washing and improper cleaning of utensils and storage containers.

The findings of this study highlight the need for improved handling and storage practices among street vendors of ready-to-eat Moringa *oleifera* leaves in Birnin Kebbi metropolis. This may be achieved through training programs that educate vendors on proper food handling and storage

techniques, as well as regular monitoring and enforcement of food safety standards by regulatory authorities.

Furthermore, the study suggests that the nutritional quality of street-vended ready-to-eat *Moringa oleifera* leaves can be improved through proper storage and handling practices. This may involve the use of shaded areas or refrigerated storage containers to preserve the delicate micronutrients found in the leaves [15] and [16]. Additionally, vendors may consider adopting good agricultural practices, such as proper washing and drying of the leaves, to reduce microbial contamination.

Overall, this study highlights the importance of assessing the nutritional and microbial quality of street-vended foods, particularly in regions where they are a significant component of the diet. The findings of this study may be used to inform policy and intervention strategies aimed at improving the safety and quality of street-vended foods, and ultimately protecting the health and well-being of consumers.

5.0 Conclusion

In conclusion, the study of street-vended ready-to-eat *Moringa oleifera* leaves in Birnin Kebbi Metropolis revealed significant variations in nutritional and microbial quality. This underscores the need for improved handling and storage practices to minimize microbial contamination and preserve nutritional quality. The findings have critical implications for public health, suggesting education on proper handling, storage, microbial testing and training on Good Hygiene Practices and Good Manufacturing Practices can ensure safety and quality.

The analysis of Moringa leaves from five vending zones provided valuable insights into nutritional value and safety. Results showed variations in moisture, ash, fibre, lipid, protein and carbohydrate content. Notably, micronutrient analysis revealed substantial beta-carotene, vitamin C, calcium and iron levels, highlighting Moringa's potential as a rich source of essential nutrients. However, bacterial contamination, including *Escherichia coli*, *Corynebacterium diphtheria* and *Listeria* spp., pose significant health risks.

The microbial contamination primarily resulted from inadequate handling, improper cleaning and storage. Addressing these concerns requires optimal handling, storage and hygiene practices among vendors. Implementing vendor training programs, enhancing regulatory oversight and enforcing food safety standards are crucial. Adopting good agricultural practices like proper washing, drying and storage techniques can minimize microbial contamination.

This research highlights the dual benefits and risks of consuming street-vended *Moringa oleifera* leaves in Birnin Kebbi. While offering valuable nutritional benefits, microbial contamination jeopardizes consumer health. Improved handling practices, enhanced regulation and public awareness campaigns will safeguard consumer well-being and optimize Moringa's nutritional benefits. Regular microbial testing and education will maximize safety, ensuring street-vended Moringa leaves contribute positively to public health.

6.0 Recommendations

To ensure the safety and quality of street-vended Moringa leaves, vendors should be educated on proper handling and storage techniques, such as storing leaves in clean containers and handling with clean hands, and undergo regular microbial testing and monitoring for pathogens and spoilage. Additionally, vendors should be trained on Good Hygiene Practices (GHPs) and Good Manufacturing Practices (GMPs) to maintain a clean production environment, including proper cleaning, sanitation, and personal hygiene practices like hand washing and waste disposal. By implementing these measures, the nutritional quality of Moringa leaves can be preserved, and the risk of microbial contamination minimized, ultimately protecting consumer health.

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8.0 Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest

9.0 References

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